
The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format
test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.
Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level C

DIFMX02_ALERT_1_C The maximum difference density is > 0.1*ZMAX*0.75
The relevant atom site should be identified.

Author Response: There is a single peak of residual electron density of negligible strength 1.18 Angstroms from O101. This peak is likely a disordered position of the water solvate that could not be adequately accounted for due to the solvate molecule lying on a symmetry special position.

PLAT094_ALERT_2_C Ratio of Maximum / Minimum Residual Density 3.60 Report

Author Response: There is a single peak of residual electron density of negligible strength 1.18 Angstroms from O101. This peak is likely a disordered position of the water solvate that could not be adequately accounted for due to the solvate molecule lying on a symmetry special position.

PLAT097_ALERT_2_C Large Reported Max. (Positive) Residual Density 0.62 eA-3

Author Response: There is a single peak of residual electron density of negligible strength 1.18 Angstroms from O101. This peak is likely a disordered position of the water solvate that could not be adequately accounted for due to the solvate molecule lying on a symmetry special position.

PLAT338_ALERT_4_C Small Aver Tau in Cyclohexane C6 -C11 34.51 Degree

Alert level G

PLAT007_ALERT_5_G	Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms	1	Report
PLAT012_ALERT_1_G	N.O.K. _shelx_res_checksum Found in CIF		Please Check
PLAT158_ALERT_4_G	The Input Unitcell is NOT Standard/Reduced		Please Check
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O1 .	109.4	Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O20 .	60.6	Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O22 .	60.8	Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O24 .	61.8	Degree
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C5 (Sohnke SpGr)		S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C6 (Sohnke SpGr)		S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C7 (Sohnke SpGr)		S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C8 (Sohnke SpGr)		R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C11 (Sohnke SpGr)		S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C12 (Sohnke SpGr)		S Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C13 (Sohnke SpGr)		S Verify

PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C14	(Sohnke SpGr)	R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C16	(Sohnke SpGr)	R Verify
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity		4.2 Low

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
4 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
17 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

2 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
6 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
1 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
11 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

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